

Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of 4-aryl-5-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-3-thio-1,2,4-dithiazolidines

M. G. Dhonde^a and S. P. Deshmukh^{b*}

^aShri Mathuradas Mohota College of Science, Urner Road, Nagpur-440 009, Maharashtra, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Shri Shivaji College, Akola-444 001, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : madhudash2001@yahoo.co.in

Fax : 91-0724-2450722

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Abstract : 4-Aryl-5-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-3-thio-1,2,4-dithiazolidines have been prepared by the interaction of *N*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride and ammonium aryl dithiocarbamates. Antimicrobial activities of these compounds were evaluated. The identities of these new *N*-glucosides have been established on the basis of usual chemical transformations, IR, NMR and mass spectral studies.

Keywords : *N*-Glycosylated cyclic compounds.

Recently, we have reported synthesis of several 4-aryl-5-phenylimino-3-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines involving interaction of 1-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-3-aryl thiocarbamides and *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride¹. In our laboratory *N*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride has been prepared² for the first time by the interaction of *N*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate with calculated quantity of chlorine.

In view of our interest in *N*-glucosylated cyclic compounds we now report the synthesis of 4-aryl-5-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-3-thio-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (**3**).

Results and discussion

The reactions of *N*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (**1**) and ammonium aryl dithiocarbamates (**2a-g**) were carried out in cold dry chloroform over 24 h (Scheme 1). The solvent was distilled off and the resulting sticky mass isolated as a residue. This when triturated several times with petroleum ether was converted to granular yellow solid. This solid was dissolved in ethanol, basified with cold ammonium hydroxide solution and finally were crystallized from ethanol to furnish **3a-g**. The products were found

non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline lead acetate solution. The specific rotation³ was measured in chloroform. The purity of products was checked by TLC and recorded the R_f values⁴.

Microbial activity (antibacterial activity) :

The compounds were screened for their antibacterial activities against various pathogenic bacteria such as *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus mirabilis* and *Salmonella typhi* by the disc method⁵ at a concentration 10 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in DMF. Amongst the compounds tested for the antibacterial activity, compounds **3f** and **3g** showed higher activity and other compounds showed moderate activity (Table 1).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. All products were crystallized from ethanol before recording the physical data. Optical rotations were measured at 38 °C. IR spectra⁶ were recorded in the range 4000–200 cm^{-1} . ¹H NMR spectra⁷ were obtained at 300 MHz for solutions in CDCl₃ (reference to TMS). The FAB mass spectra⁸ were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer/data system using argon/xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage was 10 kV, and the spectra were recorded at room temperature. *m*-Nitrobenzyl alcohol (NBA) was used as the matrix unless specified otherwise.

Bz = C₆H₅CO- (Benzoyl)R = (a) Phenyl, (b) *p*-Tolyl, (c) *o*-Tolyl, (d) *m*-Tolyl, (e) *o*-ClPh, (f) *m*-ClPh, (g) *p*-ClPh

Scheme 1

Thin layer chromatography was conducted on E. Merck TLC aluminium sheet silica gel 60 F₂₅₄.

Table 1. Antibacterial activities of compounds

Comps.	<i>E. coli</i> (mm)	<i>S. typhi</i> (mm)	<i>P. mirabilis</i> (mm)	<i>S. aureus</i> (mm)
3a	6.7	7.0	7.3	7.5
3b	7.0	7.2	7.5	8.0
3c	7.2	7.5	7.8	7.0
3d	7.4	7.6	7.5	7.5
3e	8.0	7.2	7.8	8.0
3f	8.5	8.8	9.0	10.0
3g	9.0	8.5	10.5	11.0
Co-trimazine	11.2	11.5	10.9	11.8

The required *N*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-β-*D*-glucopyranosyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (**1**) and ammonium aryl dithiocarbamates (**2a-g**) were prepared by the methods described earlier⁹.

4-Phenyl-5-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-β-*D*-glucopyranosylimino-3-thio-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (3a): The reaction of *N*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-β-*D*-glucopyranosyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (**1**) (3.54 g, 0.005 mol) (*R_f*, 0.52; 1 : 1 : 2; EtOAc : *n*-BuOH : acetone) and ammonium phenyl dithiocarbamate (**2a**) (0.93 g, 0.005 mol) was carried out in cold dry chloroform (mL) for 24 h. The chloroform was then evaporated to leave sticky syrup that was triturated with petroleum ether until a yellow solid resulted. The solid was dissolved in ethanol and basified with cold ammonium hydroxide solution to give **3a** (3.5 g, 85%); recrystallized from ethanol had m.p. 110 °C; [α]_D³⁸ +75.86° (*c*, 0.1125 in CHCl₃). The purity of the product was checked by TLC and recorded *R_f*, 0.80; (1 : 1 : 2; *n*-BuOH : *n*-hexane : acetone); IR (KBr) : ν 3062.5 (Ar-H),

2965.9 (C-H, aliphatic), 1731 (C=O), 1649.5 (C=N), 1269.5 (C-O), 1102 (C=S), 1030.8 (-S-C(=S)-N-), 891.3 (glucopyranosyl ring deformation), 767.6 (C-S), 708.1 (mono substituted phenyl ring), 494 (S-S) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR data (CDCl₃) : δ 8.05–6.92 (25H, m, Ar-H), 5.34–4.29 (5H, m, β-*D*-glucopyranosyl ring), 4.5–4.1 (2H, d, CH₂O); MS *m/z* 804 (M⁺), 777 (M-C₂H₃), 698 (M-C₆H₅-CHO), 595 (TBGNH₂⁺), 579 (TBG⁺ = C₃₄H₂₇O₉⁺), 459 (TBG-C₆H₄COO), 165 (C₉H₉O₃⁺), 121 (C₆H₅COO⁺), 105 (C₆H₅CO⁺) (Found : C, 62.50; H, 3.75; N, 3.75; S, 11.62. Calcd. for C₄₂H₃₂N₂O₉S₃ : C, 62.68; H, 3.98; N, 3.48; S, 11.94%).

When the reaction of *N*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-β-*D*-glucopyranosyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride was extended to several other ammonium aryl dithiocarbamates, corresponding 4-aryl-5-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-β-*D*-glucopyranosylimino-3-thio-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (**3b-g**) have been isolated.

4-*p*-Tolyl-5-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-β-*D*-glucopyranosylimino-3-thio-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (3b): Yield 3.2 g, (78%), m.p. 92–94 °C; [α]_D³⁸ +173.580 (*c*, 0.1308 in CHCl₃), *R_f*, 0.70; (1 : 1 : 2; *n*-BuOH : *n*-hexane : acetone); IR (KBr) : ν 3046 (Ar-H), 2929.2 (C-H aliphatic), 1730.0 (C=O), 1632.3 (C=N), 1272.3 (C-O), 1102.6 (C=S), 1023.2 (-S-C(=S)-N-), 850.3 (glucopyranosyl ring deformation), 795.4 (1,4-disubstituted ring), 767.6 (C-S), 710.3 (mono substituted phenyl ring), 492.4 (S-S) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR data (CDCl₃) : δ 8.0–7.0 (24H, m, Ar-H), 5.3–4.2 (5H, m, β-*D*-glucopyranosyl ring), 4.5–4.0 (2H, d, CH₂O), 2.4–1.7 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃); MS *m/z* 818 (M⁺), 777 (M-C₃H₅), 729 (M-C₇H₇), 714 (M-C₆H₄CO), 690 (M-C₉H₆N), 668 (M-C₈H₈NS), 639 (TBGNHC(=S)-H⁺), 595 (TBGNH⁺), 579 (TBG⁺ = C₃₄H₂₇O₉⁺), 500 (TBG-C₆H₇), 475 (TBG-C₆H₄CO), 457 (TBG-C₆H₅COOH), 424 (TBG-C₁₂H₁₁),

353 (TBG-C₁₄H₁₀O₃), 331 (TBG-C₁₄H₁₆O₄), 121 (C₆H₅COO⁺), 106 (C₆H₅CHO⁺) (Found : C, 62.95; H, 4.10; N, 3.20; S, 11.34. Calcd. for C₄₃H₃₄N₂O₉S₃ : C, 63.00; H, 4.15; N, 3.42; S, 11.73%).

4-o-Tolyl-5-tetra-O-benzoyl-β-D-glucopyranosylimino-3-thio-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (3c) : Yield 3.0 g, (73%), m.p. 97 °C (d); [α]_D³⁸ +35° (c, 0.16 in CHCl₃), R_f, 0.77; (1 : 1 : 2; *n*-BuOH : *n*-hexane : acetone) (Found : C, 62.62; H, 4.05; N, 3.22; S, 11.46. Calcd. for C₄₃H₃₄N₂O₉S₃ : C, 63.00; H, 4.15; N, 3.42; S, 11.73%).

4-m-Tolyl-5-tetra-O-benzoyl-β-D-glucopyranosylimino-3-thio-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (3d) : Yield 2.5 g, (61%), m.p. 94 °C; [α]_D³⁸ +143.14° (c, 0.1145 in CHCl₃), R_f, 0.81; (1 : 1 : 2; *n*-BuOH : *n*-hexane : acetone) (Found : C, 62.78; H, 4.17; N, 3.70; S, 11.62. Calcd. for C₄₃H₃₄N₂O₉S₃ : C, 63.00; H, 4.15; N, 3.42; S, 11.73%).

4-o-Chloro-phenyl-5-tetra-O-benzoyl-β-D-glucopyranosylimino-3-thio-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (3e) : Yield 2.3 g, (78%), m.p. 75 °C (d); [α]_D³⁸ +135.9° (c, 0.1424 in CHCl₃), R_f, 0.86; (1 : 1 : 2; *n*-BuOH : *n*-hexane : acetone); IR (KBr) : ν 3056.7 (Ar-H), 2931.3 (C-H aliphatic), 1729.3 (C=O), 1632.0 (C=N), 1271.3 (C-O), 1101.0 (C=S), 1045.4 (-S-C(=S)-N-), 868.0 (glucopyranosyl ring deformation), 787.0 (C-S), 765.0 (1,2-disubstituted ring), 709.5 (mono substituted phenyl ring), 577.7 (S-S) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR data (CDCl₃) : δ 8.05-7.7 (4H, m, Cl-Ar-H), 7.5-6.8 (20H, m, Ar-H), 5.41-4.03 (5H, m, β-D-glucopyranosyl ring), 4.4-4.0 (2H, d, CH₂O); MS *m/z* 839 (M⁺), 803 (M-Cl), 795 (M-C=S), 749 (M-NCS₂), 714 (M-C₆H₃NCl), 706 (M-C₆H₁₁NCl), 700 (C₇H₅NCl), 684 (M-C₇H₇S₂), 668 (M-C₇H₅NSCl), 639 (TBGNHC(=S)-H⁺), 607 (TBGN=CH₂⁺), 579 (TBG⁺=C₃₄H₂₇O₉⁺), 546 (TBG-CH₃OH₂), 475 (TBG-C₆H₄CO), 424 (TBG-C₇H₇O₄), 391 (TBG-C₁₂H₁₂O₂), 371 (TBG-C₁₄H₈O₂), 335 (TBG-C₁₄H₁₂O₄), 105 (C₆H₅CO⁺) (Found : C, 60.01; H, 4.00; Cl, 4.00; N, 3.75; S, 11.22. Calcd. for C₄₂H₃₄ClN₂O₉S₃ : C, 60.07, H, 3.69; Cl, 4.23; N, 3.34%).

4-m-Chloro-phenyl-5-tetra-O-benzoyl-β-D-glucopyranosylimino-3-thio-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (3f) : Yield 2.2 g, (52%), m.p. 113 °C; [α]_D³⁸ +159.95° (c, 0.1508 in CHCl₃); R_f 0.88; (1 : 1 : 2; *n*-BuOH : *n*-hexane : acetone) (Found : C, 59.75; H, 3.59; Cl, 4.07; N, 3.68; S, 11.15. Calcd. for C₄₂H₃₄ClN₂O₉S₃; C, 60.07; H, 3.69; Cl, 4.23; N, 3.34; S, 11.45%).

4-p-Chloro-phenyl-5-tetra-O-benzoyl-β-D-glucopyranosylimino-3-thio-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (3e) : Yield 3.5 g, (83%), m.p. 115-117 °C; [β]_D³⁸ +97.19° (c, 0.1089 in

CHCl₃); R_f 0.84; (1 : 1 : 2; *n*-BuOH : *n*-hexane : acetone) (Found : C, 59.98; H, 3.48; Cl, 3.93; N, 3.25; S, 11.35. Calcd. for C₄₂H₃₄ClN₂O₉S₃ : C, 60.07, H, 3.69; Cl, 4.23; N, 3.34; S, 11.45%).

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